

On Approximations and Homothetic Behavior in Mean Curvature Flow

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1 Introduction

Geometric flows are a class of processes that describe the evolution of geometric objects in time. These flows are often driven by intrinsic or extrinsic characteristics, and are often used to simplify complex geometric shapes. One of the most studied geometric flows is the mean curvature flow, where the time evolution of the surface at each point is given by

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{M}_t}{\partial t}\right)^\perp = H\nu,$$

where H is the mean curvature—given by half the trace of the shape operator—and ν is an evolving Gauss map. It is shown in 2 that such an evolution yields a monotone non-increasing area, implying that the surfaces tend toward minimality—a stationary point of the first variation of area—under the mean curvature flow. Thus, it becomes natural to explore the use of mean curvature flow as a numerical tool for approximating minimal surfaces, which are solutions to the classic Plateau’s problem—surfaces that can be parametrized by

$$\mathcal{M}(x, y, f(x, y)),$$

with a graphically defined Dirichlet boundary condition.

While theoretical underpinnings for mean curvature flow are well-established, analytical solutions often remain intractable due to the nature of non-linear partial differential equations. However, for graphically defined surfaces, mean curvature flow simplifies to a non-linear parabolic partial differential equation, suggesting numerical approximation as a useful tool for estimating solutions.

This paper references the work of Sawyer Jacobson in [2], by presenting the derived algorithm for estimating graphical minimal surfaces through the use of mean curvature flow. We then provide simulations, demonstrating the effectiveness of the numerical approach by including scenarios with planar and rotationally symmetric boundary conditions, as well as the estimation of minimal surfaces for complex boundary data—where analytical solutions would remain enigmatic. The results provide evidence for previously established results in graphical minimal surface theory are true, including the inheritance of planarity and symmetry from a boundary. They also highlight the

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usefulness of graphical mean curvature flow in estimating minimal surfaces, while also providing a visual representation of their evolution throughout the flow. This algorithm, however, fails when singularities arise in the flow.

In geometric flows, long-term behavior often includes singularities. Mathematicians classify these as type I or type II according to the rate at which curvature blows up. Due to the nature of infinite curvature, these points require special techniques to analyze. Thus, in section 3, by deriving and applying Huisken's monotonicity formula as well as a Shi-type estimate, we are able to demonstrate that self-shrinkers, objects that behave according to the equation:

$$\vec{H} = \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu \rangle,$$

Serve as precise models for type I singularities. This extends the scope to which mathematicians can analyze these computationally troublesome points.

2 Algorithm

Take a family of surfaces parameterized by

$$\mathcal{M}(u_1, u_2, s) = F(u_1, u_2) + s \left\langle \frac{\partial F_s}{\partial s}, \nu \right\rangle \nu(u_1, u_2),$$

where s is a compactly supported variational map and ν is a unit normal vector. Now, this family of surfaces has a first variation of area given by

$$\frac{d}{ds}[\mathcal{M}(s)] \Big|_{s=0} = - \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left\langle \frac{\partial F_s}{\partial s}, \nu \right\rangle H dA,$$

where H is the mean curvature. So, we choose F_s such that

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial F_s}{\partial s}, \nu \right\rangle = H(F_s),$$

yielding the monotone non-increasing

$$\frac{d}{ds}[\mathcal{M}(s)] \Big|_{s=0} = - \int_{\mathcal{M}} H^2 dA,$$

with equilibrium at $H = 0$. This motivates our definition of mean curvature flow.

Definition 1 (Mean Curvature Flow). Given a family of surfaces $\{\mathcal{M}_t\}$, the mean curvature flow is the evolution of the surface by the system

$$\begin{cases} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{M}_t}{\partial t} \right)^\perp = H\nu \\ \mathcal{M}_0 = \mathcal{M}. \end{cases}$$

Now, it was shown in [2] that a minimal surface \mathcal{M} parameterized by $\mathcal{M}(x, y, f(x, y))$ must satisfy the partial differential equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_x}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{f_y}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right) = 0.$$

So, in pair with the Dirichlet boundary condition, we get that a graphical solution to Plateau's problem in Ω is given by the system

$$\begin{cases} \operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla f}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega \\ \mathcal{M}(x, y, t) = \Gamma(x, y) & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases}$$

As our mean curvature flow is monotone non-increasing, flows will generally tend towards minimality³, implying the usefulness of such a flow to estimate minimal surfaces. In our graphical case, the mean curvature flow evolution simplifies to the system

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} = \sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2} \operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla f}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right) & \text{in } \Omega \times (0, \infty) \\ f(x, y, t) = \Gamma(x, y) & \text{on } \partial\Omega \times (0, \infty) \\ f(x, y, 0) = \rho(x, y) & \text{in } \bar{\Omega} \times \{0\} \end{cases}$$

for some function $\rho(x, y) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $\rho = \Gamma$ on $\partial\Omega$.

2.1 Simulations

Now that we have a way to estimate graphical minimal surfaces, we aim to simulate multiple cases. *All simulations and visualizations were implemented in Mathematica.*

2.1.1 Inheritance of Planarity

In [2], it was shown that graphical minimal surfaces $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ with boundary $\Gamma \subseteq \pi$, for some plane π , will be such that $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \pi$. Therefore, we look to simulate such cases for $\mathcal{M}_t, t \in [0, T)$. In this simulation, we use the initial surface data $f(0, x, y) := \sin(\frac{\pi x}{5}) \sin(\frac{\pi y}{5})$. We also fix a uniformly-zero Dirichlet boundary condition on $[0, 5] \times [0, 5]$. Then, we let the surface flow, governed by the partial differential equation in 2. We see, as expected, a smoothing effect, as the surface tends towards its planar boundary.

As expected, \mathcal{M}_t converged to a subset of π , with $\partial\mathcal{M}_t = \Gamma \subseteq \pi$, exhibiting the property shown in [2].

³A counterexample occurs when a surface yields singularities.

2.1.2 Inheritance of Rotational Symmetry

It was also shown in [2] that graphical minimal surfaces $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$, a rotationally symmetric boundary Γ , induces rotational symmetry on \mathcal{M} . It is therefore interesting to simulate such cases. When the boundary Γ can be embedded in a plane, this property is trivial as all planes are symmetric. So, we take the non-planar boundary data $\Gamma = 0.1(x - 2.5)^2 - 0.1(y - 2.5)^2 + 0.8$, which represents the boundary of a hyperbolic paraboloid in \mathbb{R}^3 . We also must define the initial boundary data, which we choose to be non-symmetric to exhibit how the symmetry of the boundary truly imposes such a property on \mathcal{M} .

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(0, x, y) := & 0.1(x - 2.5)^2 - 0.1(y - 2.5)^2 + 0.8 + 0.25 \exp(-((x - 3.0)^2 + (y - 3.2)^2)) \\
 & + 0.2 \exp(-((x - 1.5)^2 + (y - 2.0)^2)) \\
 & + 0.15 \exp(-((x - 4.0)^2 + (y - 1.0)^2)) . \\
 & + 0.1 \sin(2x) \cos(1.2y) + 0.05 \sin(3y) \cos(1.5x) .
 \end{aligned}$$

After a short period of time, we see that the surface begins to evolve towards symmetry. Finally, it converges to the hyperbolic paraboloid, spanning the boundary defined above.

As expected, the surface \mathcal{M} exhibits two-fold rotational symmetry, just as does its boundary.

2.1.3 Complex Boundary Data

One of the primary applications of graphical mean curvature flow is to estimate minimal surfaces with complicated boundary data. Therefore, we apply our algorithm to simulate such cases under multiple boundary conditions. So, we define a complicated boundary:

$$0.2 \sin(2x) \cos(1.5y) + 0.15 \sin(3y) \cos(1.2x) + 0.1 \exp(-((x-2)^2 + (y-3)^2)) \\ - 0.08 \exp(-((x-3.5)^2 + (y-1.5)^2)) + 0.05 \sin(xy) + 0.5,$$

with initial condition:

$$\Gamma = 0.2 \sin(2x) \cos(1.5y) + 0.15 \sin(3y) \cos(1.2x) + 0.1 \exp(-((x-2)^2 + (y-3)^2)) \\ - 0.08 \exp(-((x-3.5)^2 + (y-1.5)^2)) + 0.05 \sin(xy) + 0.5 + 0.2 \exp(-((x-1.2)^2 + (y-1.5)^2)) \\ + 0.15 \exp(-((x-3.5)^2 + (y-3)^2)) + 0.1 \sin(2.5x) \cos(1.8y) + 0.05 \sin(3y) \cos(2x) \\ + 0.1 \exp(-((x-2.5)^2 + (y-2.5)^2)).$$

This is analytically difficult to solve, highlighting the importance of our algorithm in estimating such surfaces.

(a) Initial Data

(b) Intermediate Data

(c) Final Data

We see that the surface flows, eventually converging, giving us an estimate of the minimal spanning surface for the given boundary condition.

3 Self-Shrinker Singularity Model for Mean Curvature Flow

Though the graphical boundary case exhibits predictable behavior, at least in short time frames, the general case is far more complicated. One common occurrence is the emanation of a singularity. These can be classified as either type I or type II according to the rate at which they blow up, but for our purposes, we will only define the following:

Definition 2 (Type I Singularity). Let T be the time of the first singularity. A type I singularity is such that

$$\exists C : \sup_{\mathcal{M}_t} |h|^2(x, t) \leq \frac{C}{T-t},$$

for $t \in (0, T)$.

Singularities do appear occasionally in graphical mean curvature flows; however, they are far more common in the general case. To analyze these complicated shapes, we often need to find a way to model them. Specifically, we aim to establish a model for type I singularities. To do so, we must first prove the following.

Theorem 3 (Huisken's Monotonicity Formula).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi = - \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \vec{H} - \frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} \right|^2 \Phi d\text{Vol},$$

where Φ is the backwards heat kernel.

Proof. Recall the backwards heat kernel,

$$\Phi(x, t) = \frac{1}{(-4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} e^{\frac{|x|^2}{4t}},$$

satisfying the backwards heat equation

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + \text{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = 0.$$

Now, note that $\sigma = \frac{\Phi}{\sqrt{-t}}$ solves the backwards heat equation as well. So, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \Phi &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) (\sqrt{-t} \sigma) \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \sqrt{-t} \right) \sigma + \sqrt{-t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

Now since σ is a solution to the backwards heat equation, this simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \Phi &= \sigma \frac{-1}{2\sqrt{-t}} \\ &= \frac{\Phi}{2t}. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Now, we decompose the induced Laplacian on the sub-manifold into the ambient Laplacian and the normal part as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \text{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} - \nabla_{\nu\nu}^2 \right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi}.$$

By (6), we attain

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla\right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \frac{\Phi}{2t} - \operatorname{Hess}(\Phi)(\nu, \nu) + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi}. \quad (2)$$

Now, we see

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 \log \Phi(\nu, \nu) &= \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla \Phi}{\Phi} \right) (\nu, \nu) \\ &= \frac{\nabla^2 \Phi(\nu, \nu)}{\Phi} - \frac{\nabla_\nu \Phi \otimes \nabla_\nu \Phi}{\Phi^2} \\ &= \frac{\nabla^2 \Phi(\nu, \nu)}{\Phi} - \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\operatorname{Hess}(\Phi)(\nu, \nu) + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \Phi \operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi)(\nu, \nu). \quad (3)$$

So, substituting (8), into (7), we obtain

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla\right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \frac{\Phi}{2t} - \Phi \operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi)(\nu, \nu). \quad (4)$$

We know the form of Φ , so we calculate the logarithm of Φ to be $c(t) + \frac{|x|^2}{4t}$. We thus have

$$\operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi) = \operatorname{Hess} \frac{|x|^2}{4t}.$$

Since t is said to be fixed in computation, we have

$$\operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi)(\nu, \nu) = \frac{1}{2t}.$$

Plugging this into (9), we see

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla\right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Now, it is shown in [1] that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} = \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Phi - H^2 \Phi \right) \, d\operatorname{Vol}.$$

We can insert a Laplacian due to the integration by parts formula like so:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} &= \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathcal{M}_t} \right) \Phi - H^2 \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + 2 \langle \nabla \Phi, \vec{H} \rangle + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi - H^2 \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi$ is the divergence of the background gradient⁴.

Now, completing the square,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} = \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi - \left| \vec{H} - \frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} \right|^2 \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} \, d\operatorname{Vol}.$$

By (10), this simplifies to

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} = - \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \vec{H} - \frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} \right|^2 \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol}.$$

□

Remark 3.1. Given

$$\Phi = c(t) \frac{|x|^2}{4t} \exp\left(\frac{|x|^2}{4t}\right),$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \Phi &= c(t) \frac{\nabla |x|^2}{4t} \exp\left(\frac{|x|^2}{4t}\right) \\ &= \Phi \frac{x}{2t}. \end{aligned}$$

So,

$$\frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} = \frac{\langle x, \nu \rangle}{2t}.$$

Lemma 4. Let $\{\mathcal{M}_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ be a mean curvature flow with $|h| \leq C$ for $t \in [0, T]$. Then, $\exists C_1(C, T)$ such that $|\nabla h| \leq C_1$ on $[\frac{T}{2}, T]$.

Proof. We look to prove this lemma through a Shi-type estimate. To start, we consider $\varsigma(t, x) = \alpha|h|^2 + t|\nabla h|^2$, for some $\alpha > 0$. Now, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \varsigma &= \alpha \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) |h|^2 + |\nabla h|^2 + t \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) |\nabla h|^2 \\ &= -2\alpha |\nabla h|^2 + 2\alpha |h|^4 + |\nabla h|^2 + t(-2|\nabla^2 h|^2 + \epsilon), \end{aligned}$$

where ϵ is an error term comprised of low order terms. Rearranging,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \varsigma = 2\alpha |h|^4 - 2\alpha |\nabla h|^2 + |\nabla h|^2 - 2t|\nabla^2 h|^2 + t\epsilon.$$

Now, by the assumption of a bounded curvature estimate and the work of [1] to show that the error is bounded, we have the inequality

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \varsigma \leq 2\alpha C^4 + (1 - 2\alpha + tDC^2) |\nabla h|^2.$$

⁴The divergence of the background gradient can be decomposed: $\operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t}(\nabla \Phi) = \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t}(\nabla^{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi + \nabla^\perp \Phi) = \Delta_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi + \langle \vec{H}, \nabla \Phi \rangle$.

Now, we pick α such that for our largest case, $t = T$,

$$\frac{1 + TDC^2}{2} < \alpha.$$

Thus,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \varsigma \leq 2\alpha C^4.$$

Now, by the parabolic maximum principle,

$$\begin{aligned} \varsigma(t, x) &\leq 2\alpha C^4 T + \varsigma(0, x) \\ &\leq 2\alpha C^4 T + \alpha C^2. \end{aligned}$$

Now, recalling our definition for $\varsigma(t, x)$, we have

$$t|\nabla h|^2 \leq 2\alpha C^4 T + \alpha C^2, \forall t \in [0, T].$$

Thus, we have an a priori bound

$$|\nabla h| \leq C_1(T, C), \forall t \in \left[\frac{T}{2}, T \right].$$

□

Now, we are able to prove the main result.

Theorem 5 (Self-shrinkers as a Model for Type I Singularities). Let $\{\mathcal{M}_t\}_{t < T} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ be a smooth mean curvature flow. Suppose (x_0, T) is a type I singularity. Then, for all sequences $\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty$, the rescaled flows

$$\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)} := \lambda_k \left(\mathcal{M}_{T + \lambda_k^{-2}s} - x_0 \right), s < 0$$

sub-sequentially converge smoothly to a limit flow $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_s$, which satisfies the self-shrinker equation

$$\vec{H} = \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu \rangle.$$

Geometrically, this represents a shape-preserving property under uniform shrinking.

Proof. Recall for a type I singularity, we have C such that

$$\sup_{\mathcal{M}_t} |h|^2(x, t) \leq \frac{C}{T - t},$$

for $t \in (0, T)$. After a parabolic rescaling, we have

$$T - t = -\lambda_k^{-2}s.$$

So,

$$|h_{\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)}}| = \frac{1}{\lambda_k} |h_{\mathcal{M}_t}| \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \frac{C}{\sqrt{T - t}} = \frac{C}{-s}, \forall k.$$

By lemma 4, curvature and its derivatives are bounded uniformly in k^5 . Thus, by standard compactness theorems

$$\exists \{k_n\} \rightarrow \infty : \mathcal{M}_s^{(k_n)} \xrightarrow{C_{\text{loc}}^\infty} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_s.$$

Now, by theorem 3,

$$\theta_{(x_0, T)}(t) = \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi(x, t) d\text{Vol}$$

is monotone non-increasing in t . Also, substituting 3.1 into 3 and applying, we obtain

$$\frac{d}{dt} \theta_{x_0, T}(t) = - \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \vec{H} + \frac{(x - x_0)^\perp}{2(T - t)} \right|^2 \Phi(x, t) d\text{Vol}.$$

Consider $t_1 < t_2$ and integrate above. We now have,

$$\theta(t_2) - \theta(t_1) = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \vec{H} + \frac{(x - x_0)^\perp}{2(T - t)} \right|^2 \Phi(x, t) d\text{Vol} dt$$

We now change variables to the rescaled setting for $a < b < 0$. This yields

$$\theta_{x_0, T}(T + \lambda_k^{-2}b) - \theta_{x_0, T}(T + \lambda_k^{-2}a) = \int_a^b \int_{\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)}} \left| \vec{H}^{(k)} - \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu^{(k)} \rangle \right|^2 \Phi(x) d\text{Vol} ds.$$

Observe when $\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty, t_1, t_2 \rightarrow T$. So, as $k_n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\int_a^b \int_{\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)}} \left| \vec{H}^{(k)} - \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu^{(k)} \rangle \right|^2 \Phi(x) d\text{Vol} ds = 0,$$

for any $a < b < 0^6$. Hence, $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_s$ satisfies $\vec{H} = \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \tilde{\nu} \rangle$ and it must be a self-shrinker. \square

References

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- [2] Jacobson, S., On Graphical Minimal Surfaces and the Homotheticity of Singular Behavior in Mean Curvature Flow, *Zenodo*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16903054> (2025).

⁵It is known that when curvature is bounded, all higher derivatives are as well.

⁶We know $\theta_{x_0, t}(T)$ is defined because $\Phi \geq 0$ and monotone non-increasing.